

A STUDY ON BRAND PREFERENCE & BRAND SATISFACTION OF REFRIGERATOR

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Abstract:

A brand is essential for businesses of all sizes because it increases value, gives employees direction and motivation, and makes acquiring new customers easier. One of the significant components of a brand is a logo because people instantly recognize it as the ‘face’ of a business. A professional logo design is simple enough to be memorable but powerful enough to give a company’s desired impression. The finished logo is simple enough to be memorable but powerful enough to make the right impression. Just as people are likely to purchase from a business that appears polished and legitimate, families need to feel comfortable before committing to a product. Consumer durables are those products which do not wear out quickly and can be used for a long period. Today so many brands of consumer durables are available in the market. Brand & price are two most important variables which influence consumer’s decision regarding purchase of consumer durables. The studies observe Brand preference & satisfaction of Refrigerator. The implement adopted for the collection of data was the questionnaire. The sample size is 100 respondents. Convenient sampling method is used to test the research. This study used in percentage analysis for factors influence brand preference & brand satisfaction of refrigerator. This research of the study conducted in Coimbatore district.

Key Words: Brand, Branding, Brand Preference, Brand Satisfaction

Introduction:

Consumer durables are those products which do not wear out quickly and can be used for a long period. Today so many brands of consumer durables are available in the market. Brand & price are two most important variables which influence consumer’s decision regarding purchase of consumer durables. “Brand is a name that influences buyers”. While purchasing a single consumer durable, people generally come across so many brands. The present study is intended to find out different brands used and preferred by consumers in the market. People tend to buy quality products or top brands when it comes to consumer durables. But price sometimes becomes a barrier. So it is seen that people tend to compare brands with price. Because there are customers who are willing to buy several trusted brands of consumer durables but because of high price they cannot afford to purchase those. It is also seen that some consumers are very much loyal to some brands when it comes to consumer durables. The study also focuses on those consumers in the sense that what propels them to buy only selected brands i.e., to find out the reasons for brand preference. In today’s marketplace teeming with thousands of products and services, all of which are being commoditized, a brand stands out from the clutter and attracts attention. A brand name can create and stand for loyalty, trust, faith, premium-less or mass-market appeal, depending on how the brand is advertised and promoted. A brand differentiates a product from similar products and enables it to charge a higher premium in return for identity and greater faith in its function. A brand is also likely to survive longer than just an undifferentiated product. A brand is akin to a living being; it has an identity, personality, name, culture, vision, emotion, and intelligence. The brand owner confers all these. It and needs to be continuously looked at to keep the brand relevant to the target it intends to sell.

Brand Preference:

Brand preference represents which brands are preferred under assumptions of equality in price and availability. Brand preference measures quantify the impact of marketing activities in customers’ hearts and minds and potential customers. Higher brand preference usually indicates revenues and profit, making it an indicator of company financial performance. It signifies desirability or selection of an alternative. It can be further seen as a consumer’s predisposition towards a brand that varies according to the cognitive, affective and cognitive effects that the brand has had on the consumer. Understanding the pattern of consumer preference can be critical for a brand’s success. To drive preference towards a brand, marketers strategies to improve top-of-mind awareness and increase the probability that the brand is included in the consideration set.

Brand Satisfaction:

Satisfaction is often used as a predictor of future consumer purchases. Satisfied customers have a higher likelihood of repeating purchases in time, recommending that others try the source of satisfaction and becoming less receptive to the competitor’s offerings. Specifically, satisfaction is found to be a necessary precursor of

customer loyalty. Whereas most studies strongly relate satisfaction and loyalty, some consider the relationship to be interchangeable. Some to be unidirectional that is, progressing from satisfaction to loyalty only, satisfied customers tend to be loyal customers with or without the mediation of other variables.

Review of Literature:

Kalyanasundaram and Sangeetha (2019) aimed to determine the brand preference and consumption of refrigerators, determine the influence of media on consumption, and ascertain the impact of promotional tools on brand preference. The scope of the study was based on the preference of refrigerator users' in Ariyamangalam, Kattur. Fifty sample respondents from Ariyamangalam and Kattur district. The convenience sampling method applied, and percentage analysis used for the study. The findings reveal the effectiveness and usage of the refrigerator by brands. Brands attract customers by helping them to distinguish among the goods and services available on the market. Therefore, the branding process is of the essence for the functioning of market-oriented economies.

Ganesan (2018) identified the factors influencing purchasing kitchen Appliances by analysing the sources of knowledge of the kitchen appliances brands. Under the convenience sampling method, 60 sample respondents were selected in Tiruvarur Town. Every manufacturer aiming to increase sales must understand consumers' behaviour to satisfy the consumer wishes. The study suggested adequate market demand for home appliances, and the potential consumers are well aware of the necessity of such products. While launching a product, it would be better for the company to follow the penetration pricing policy to penetrate the market since potential buyers are price sensitive. As far as product technology is concerned, it would be better for the company to follow the 'trading down' policy to cover the lower-income group to the maximum extent.

Sugundhan et al. (2018) analyzed customer satisfaction factors in household appliances and understood the customer preferences of household appliances' satisfaction factors. One hundred samples were used in this analysis. Descriptive statistics, T-test, ANOVA were the statistical tools applied in this study. The study investigated customer's satisfaction in a household appliance. The study results also highlighted that customer satisfaction is an underlying segment of the marketing capacity. It may be characterised by the number of customers or level of aggregate customers, whose detailed involvement with a firm, its items, or its administrations surpasses determined fulfilled objectives.

Subhadeep (2016) investigated consumer durables brands primarily preferred in the market and identified the factors that affect consumer durables' brand preference. The study was conducted in Tinsukia town, taking 371 households as the sample. The quota sampling technique was adopted. Chi-square and percentage analysis were applied in this study. The study concluded that cost-effectiveness, brand name, product design, advertisement, friend's advice, and after-sales services influencing consumers' brand preference. It also reveals that customers are satisfied and loyal to the brands of consumer durables they are using. Therefore, the study is essential as marketers can strategize consumer buying behaviour and consumers to avail of quality products.

Tharani et al. (2017) aim to know the awareness of electronic goods, know the level of satisfaction, study electronic goods usage, and knowledgeable customer involvement. The study was conducted in Coimbatore city. A proportionate random sampling method was adopted by taking ten per cent with the sample size resulting in 110 respondents. The percentage method, weighted average method and Chi-square method were applied. The study suggested, now day products are customized to digital. On this occasion, the idea must be built for a better brand image, and the quality must be checked frequently for better customer satisfaction. Regular communication and announcement of products to the customers by using advanced media techniques are inevitable.

Objectives:

- To study the brand preference to purchase of refrigerator.
- To identify the factors that influence brand preference to purchase of Refrigerator.
- To analyze the factors of satisfaction level of consumers with usage of Refrigerator.

Methodology of the Study:

The study follows both primary and secondary data. The primary data is derived by means of well designed questionnaire. The secondary data is collected from books, journals, magazine, press and internet. The study followed by 100 respondents from Pollachi Taluk, Coimbatore district. The convenience sampling method chooses to this study and Simple Percentage, ANOVA & Friedman Test tools applied to test the study.

Analysis and Interpretation of Study:

Simple Percentage:

Factors Influence Brand Preference:

S.No	Factors	Low %	Moderate %	High %	Total
1	Media Advertisement	23.5	30.5	46.0	100
2	Parents, Relatives and Friends	24.4	43.9	31.7	100
3	Competitive Price	33.1	34.7	32.2	100
4	Quality of the Product	22.8	33.0	44.2	100

5	Services of the Product	24.6	34.4	41.0	100
6	Cooling Performance	22.0	34.1	43.9	100
7	Durability	26.1	31.8	42.1	100
8	Available in Retail Outlet	37.4	32.7	29.9	100
9	Advance Technologies	31.3	30.8	37.9	100
10	User – Friendly	30.9	31.2	37.9	100
11	Warranty/Guaranty	30.7	32.1	37.2	100

- (46.0%) consumers have a high preference over ‘media advertisement’.
- (43.9%) consumers have a moderate preference towards ‘parents,relatives and friends’.
- (34.7%) consumers have a moderate preference towards the factor ‘competitive price’.
- (44.2%) consumers have a high preference towards the factor ‘quality of the product’.
- (41.0%) consumers have a high preference towards the ‘services of the product’.
- (43.9%) consumers have a high preference towards ‘cooling performance’.
- (42.1%) consumers have a high preference for ‘durability’.
- (37.4%) consumers have a low preference towards ‘availability in the retail outlet’.
- (37.9%) consumers have a high preference towards ‘advance technologies’.
- (37.9%) consumers have a high preference towards ‘user-friendly products’.
- (37.2%) consumers have a high preference towards ‘warranty/guaranty’.

Preference on Type of Refrigerator & Price of Refrigerator:

Preference	Description	n= 100	%
Type of Refrigerator	Single Door	76	72.8
	Double Door	24	27.2
	Total	100	100
Price of Refrigerator	Rs.5,000- Rs. 10,000	18	12.9
	Rs. 10,001 – Rs. 15,000	22	30.9
	Rs. 15,001 – Rs. 20,000	28	32.1
	Rs. 20,001 – Rs. 25,000	24	17.5
	Above Rs. 25,001	10	6.6
	Total	100	100

- **Preference for Types of Refrigerators:** Most consumers, 76 (72.8%), prefer a ‘single door’ refrigerator, and 24 (27.2%) prefer a ‘double door’ refrigerator. In conclusion, most consumers 76 (72.8%) prefer a ‘single door’ refrigerator.
- **Preference for Price of Refrigerator:** Most 28 (32.1%) consumers prefer to pay the price of ‘Rs.15,001 - Rs. 20,000’, 24 (30.9%) prefer ‘Rs. 10,001 - Rs. 15,000’, 22 (17.5%) prefer ‘Rs. 20,001 - Rs. 25,000’, 18 (12.9%) prefer ‘Rs. 5,000 - Rs. 10,000’, and 10 (6.6%) consumers prefer the price of ‘above Rs. 25,000’. In conclusion, majority, 28 (32.1%), prefer to pay the price of ‘Rs. 15,001 - Rs.20, 000’.

Factors Influencing Brand Satisfaction:

S.No	Factors	Low %	Moderate %	High %	Total
1	Price	16.9	34	49.1	100
2	Quality	14.8	41.9	43.3	100
3	Availability	21.7	33.1	45.2	100
4	After Sales Service	30.9	35.3	33.8	100
5	Promotional Offers	34	35.1	30.9	100
6	EMI Facility	31.5	36.4	32.1	100
7	Storage Space	24.2	38.5	37.3	100
8	Cooling System	21.4	39.7	38.9	100
9	Door Facility	22.6	34.9	42.5	100
10	Weight	28.1	36.7	35.2	100
11	Usage System	24.9	35.2	39.9	100
12	Capacity (Size and Liters)	29.7	35.8	34.5	100

- (49.1%), have high-level satisfaction with the ‘refrigerator’s price’.
- (43.3%) of the consumers has high satisfaction with the refrigerator’s ‘quality’.
- (45.2%), have a high level of satisfaction with the ‘availability’ of the refrigerator
- (35.3%), have a moderate level of satisfaction with the ‘after-sales service’.
- (35.1%) consumers have a moderate level of satisfaction with the ‘promotional offers’ while buying the refrigerator.
- (36.4%), have a moderate level of satisfaction with the ‘EMI facility’ while purchasing the refrigerator.
- (38.5%), have a moderate level of satisfaction in the ‘storage space’ while purchasing the refrigerator.

- (39.7%), have a moderate level of satisfaction with the ‘cooling system’ while purchasing the refrigerator.
- (42.5%) consumers have a high level of satisfaction with the ‘door facility’ while purchasing the refrigerator.
- (36.7%) consumers have a moderate level of satisfaction with the ‘weight’ while purchasing the refrigerator.
- (39.9%), have a high level of satisfaction with the ‘usage system’ while buying the refrigerator.
- (35.8%) consumers have a moderate level of satisfaction on the ‘capacity (size and litres)’ while buying the refrigerator.

Anova:

Monthly Income and Factors Influencing Brand Preference:

S.No	Factors	SS	Df	MS	X		Statistical Inference
1	Media Advertisement				G1=	4.23	
	Between Groups	10.609	4	2.652	G2=	4.18	
	Within Groups	664.429	777	0.855	G3=	3.88	
					G4=	3.77	F=3.102 0.015<0.05
					G5=	4.23	Significant
2	Parents, Relatives and Friends				G1=	4	
	Between Groups	1.615	4	0.404	G2=	4.06	
	Within Groups	565.971	777	0.728	G3=	3.96	F=0.554 0.696>0.05
					G4=	4.19	Not Significant
					G5=	4.08	
3	Competitive Price				G1=	3.92	
	Between Groups	7.671	4	1.918	G2=	4.06	
	Within Groups	597.579	777	0.769	G3=	3.68	
					G4=	3.96	F=2.493 0.042<0.05
					G5=	4.12	Significant
4	Quality of the Product				G1=	4.11	
	Between Groups	6.254	4	1.564	G2=	4.18	
	Within Groups	680.417	777	0.876	G3=	4.05	F=1.786 0.130>0.05
					G4=	4.58	Not
					G5=	4.08	Significant
5	Services of the Product				G1=	4.01	
	Between Groups	7.645	4	1.911	G2=	4.11	
	Within Groups	828.508	777	1.066	G3=	4.04	F=1.793 0.128>0.05
					G4=	4.46	Not
					G5=	3.81	Significant
6	Cooling Performance				G1=	4.2	
	Between Groups	16.975	4	4.244	G2=	4.09	
	Within Groups	686.984	777	0.884	G3=	4.16	F=4.800 0.001<0.01
					G4=	4.38	Highly Significant
					G5=	3.42	

7	Durability				G1=	4.08	
	Between Groups	7.637	4	1.909	G2=	4.09	
	Within Groups	716.793	777	0.923	G3=	4.25	F=3.070 0.018<0.05
					G4=	4.31	Significant
					G5=	3.65	

8	Available in Retail Outlet				G1=	3.79	
	Between Groups	4.168	4	1.042	G2=	3.86	
	Within Groups	820.287	777	1.056	G3=	3.79	F=0.987 0.414>0.05
					G4=	3.92	Not Significant
					G5=	3.46	

9	Advance Technologies				G1=	3.95	
	Between Groups	4.073	4	1.018	G2=	3.94	
	Within Groups	846.081	777	1.089	G3=	4.09	F=0.935 0.443>0.05
					G4=	4	Not Significant
					G5=	3.62	

10	User Friendly				G1=	3.96	
	Between Groups	7.436	4	1.859	G2=	4	
	Within Groups	770.313	777	0.991	G3=	4.11	F=1.875 0.113>0.05
					G4=	4.35	Not Significant
					G5=	3.65	

11	Warranty/Guaranty				G1=	3.89	
	Between Groups	20.647	4	5.162	G2=	3.92	
	Within Groups	947.907	777	1.22	G3=	4.09	F=4.231 0.002<0.01
					G4=	4.46	Highly Significant
					G5=	3.27	

G1=Upto Rs. 30,000, G2=Rs. 30,000-Rs. 50,000, G3=Rs. 50,000 - Rs. 80,000, G4=Rs. 80,000 - Rs. 1, 00,000, G5=Above Rs.1,00,000.

Since the p-value is greater than 0.01 and 0.05 significant level, factors that influence brand preference to purchase a refrigerator such as parents, relatives and friends, quality of the product, services of the product, and available in retail outlet user-friendly, therefore the null hypothesis can be accepted. This infers no significant variance among monthly income and parents, relatives and friends, quality of the product, services of the product, available in-retail outlet and user-friendly.

However, the p-value is less than 0.01 and 0.05 significant level, factors influencing brand preference such as media advertisement (F=3.102), competitive price (F=2.493), advanced technologies (F=0.935), cooling performance (F=4.800), durability (F=3.070), warranty/guaranty (F=4.231), the null hypothesis is rejected. This infers significant variance among monthly income and media advertisement, competitive price, advanced technologies, cooling performance, durability and warranty/guaranty.

Friedman Test:

Factors Influencing Brand Preference:

Factors	Mean Rank	Rank	Statistical Inference
Media Advertisement	6.5	1	
Parents, Relatives and Friends	5.74	9	
Competitive Price	5.65	10	
Quality of the Product	6.47	3	
Services of the Product	6.11	5	$c^2 = 177.420$
Cooling Performance	6.49	2	df = 10
Durability	6.26	4	0.000<0.01

Available in Retail Outlet	5.28	11	Highly Significant
Advance Technologies	5.85	7	
User Friendly	5.87	6	Kendall's W = 0.023
Warranty/Guaranty	5.8	8	

Since the p-value is less than the 0.01 significant level, hence there is a significant difference between mean ranks and factors influencing brand preference.

'Media advertisement' secures the first rank with the mean value of 6.50, 'cooling performance' is second (6.49), 'quality of the product' is third (6.47), 'durability' is fourth (6.26), 'services of the product' is fifth (6.11), 'user friendly' is sixth (5.87), 'advance technologies' is seventh (5.85), 'warranty and guaranty' is eighth rank (5.80), 'parents, relatives and friends' is ninth (5.74), 'competitive price' is tenth rank (5.65).

Hence, there is a significant difference between mean rank and media advertisement, parents, relatives and friends, competitive price, quality of the product, services of the product, cooling performance, durability, availability in retail outlet, advanced technologies, user friendly and warranty/guaranty.

Conclusion:

The market for consumer goods is becoming more competitive now days. From the study, majority of the respondents are satisfied with their preferred brand. According to their priority, major factors leads to purchase are quality, price, brand image, advertising and recommendations. The findings help to identify the strong and weak points of various brands and suggestion have been framed with a view to higher degree of brand awareness, satisfaction towards selected home appliances. Branding is about building consumer trust in an organization's products. Nowadays, when competition is too high firms should not disregard this and there should be a continuous investment on how to improve and how to retain their brand image and competitive position in the market. One point of general agreement is that in a highly competitive market, brands are of particular importance in catalyzing consumption and eventually increasing producers' and marketers' revenues. Brands attract customers by helping them to distinguish among the goods and services available on the market. This is why the branding process is of essence for the functioning of market-oriented economies.

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